

THE SNAKE LEMMA: A CATEGORICAL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT. The Snake Lemma is a fundamental result in homological algebra, traditionally proved by diagram chasing. We provide a detailed construction of the connecting morphism and prove the exactness of the resulting sequence using only universal properties. Most background material is standard and is included only to fix notation and keep the main proof readable.

INTRODUCTION

The Snake Lemma is a fundamental result in homological algebra, known for establishing the existence of a connecting morphism that completes an exact sequence. In the standard references, the lemma is typically proved by diagram chasing [3], which involves the manipulation of elements of the objects.

The objective of this text is to provide a detailed proof of the Snake Lemma based entirely on universal properties. This text is intended as a self-contained exposition. Most preliminary material is standard and is included only to fix notation and to make the proof of the Snake Lemma readable. We follow closely the exposition of Assem [1] and keep the argument within universal constructions. We review categories and basic classes of morphisms, and introduce the universal objects that will be used throughout: the zero object, equalizers, and pullbacks. We then discuss zero morphisms, kernels and cokernels, images and coimages, exact sequences, and strict morphisms. Next, we state the pullback properties in abelian categories and two standard diagram lemmas. Throughout, we repeatedly invoke the principle of duality to obtain the corresponding dual notions and results.

Since these preliminaries are standard, we do not reproduce their proofs. We include proofs only for two auxiliary results: one is a tailored formulation of a broader theorem yielding exactly the statement required in the main argument, and the other is a result often left as an exercise in textbook treatments.

We conclude this work with a proof of the Snake Lemma based entirely on universal properties.

1. CATEGORIES

We present the definition of a category.

1.1. Definition. A category \mathcal{C} consists of the following data:

- (1) A class, denoted by \mathcal{C}_0 or $\text{Ob } \mathcal{C}$, called the class of objects of \mathcal{C} ;
- (2) For every pair (X, Y) of objects in \mathcal{C} , a set denoted by $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ or $\text{Hom}_{\mathcal{C}}(X, Y)$, whose elements are called the morphisms from X to Y ;
- (3) For every triple (X, Y, Z) of objects in \mathcal{C} , a map

$$\mathcal{C}(X, Y) \times \mathcal{C}(Y, Z) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(X, Z)$$

which associates to $(f, g) \in \mathcal{C}(X, Y) \times \mathcal{C}(Y, Z)$ a element denoted by $g \circ f$ or, more briefly, gf , in $\mathcal{C}(X, Z)$ and called their composite. This map, called composition, satisfies the following axioms:

- (C1) Associativity: If $f \in \mathcal{C}(W, X)$, $g \in \mathcal{C}(X, Y)$, and $h \in \mathcal{C}(Y, Z)$, then $h(gf) = (hg)f$.
- (C2) Identity: To each object X of \mathcal{C} is associated a morphism 1_X in $\mathcal{C}(X, X)$ called the identity on X , such that if $f \in \mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ and $g \in \mathcal{C}(W, X)$, then $f1_X = f$ and $1_Xg = g$.

The nature of objects is disregarded. The relationships between objects, which are the morphisms, form the core of the theory. Examples of categories can be found in Jacobson [2].

Throughout this text, whenever we state that a result follows “by duality” or refer to the “dual” of a proposition, we mean that by reversing the direction of all arrows and the order of all compositions, we obtain a valid dual property. For a formal and detailed treatment of the Principle of Duality, we refer the reader to Mac Lane [3].

2. TYPES OF MORPHISMS

We now present the definitions of monomorphism, epimorphism, and isomorphism in an arbitrary category.

2.1. Definition. Let \mathcal{C} be a category.

- (a) A morphism $f: X \rightarrow Y$ in \mathcal{C} is a monomorphism if, for all morphisms $g, h: W \rightarrow X$, the equality $fg = fh$ implies $g = h$.

$$W \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{g} \\ \xrightarrow{h} \end{array} X \xrightarrow{f} Y$$

- (b) Dually, a morphism $f: X \rightarrow Y$ in \mathcal{C} is an epimorphism if, for all morphisms $g, h: Y \rightarrow Z$, the equality $gf = hf$ implies $g = h$.

$$X \xrightarrow{f} Y \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{g} \\ \xrightarrow{h} \end{array} Z$$

2.2. Proposition. Let \mathcal{C} be a category and let $f: X \rightarrow Y$, $g: Y \rightarrow Z$ be morphisms in \mathcal{C} .

- (a) If f and g are monomorphisms, then gf is a monomorphism.
(b) If gf is a monomorphism, then f is a monomorphism.

By the principle of duality, the corresponding properties hold for epimorphisms: if f and g are epimorphisms, then gf is an epimorphism; and if gf is an epimorphism, then g is an epimorphism.

2.3. Definition. Let \mathcal{C} be a category and let $f: X \rightarrow Y$ be a morphism. The morphism f is an isomorphism if there exists a morphism $f': Y \rightarrow X$ such that $f'f = 1_X$ and $ff' = 1_Y$. In this case, the objects X and Y are said to be isomorphic and we write $X \cong Y$.

In particular, every isomorphism is both a monomorphism and an epimorphism. The converse is not always true.

3. ZERO OBJECT

In the next three sections, we introduce three universal objects that will be used throughout the text: the zero object, equalizers, and pullbacks. Whenever we refer to a universal object, we intuitively mean that any other object or pair satisfying the same property must uniquely factor through it. This will become clear in the definitions of equalizer and pullbacks.

3.1. Definition. A zero object, denoted by 0 , is an object such that for every $X \in \mathcal{C}_0$ the sets $\mathcal{C}(0, X)$ and $\mathcal{C}(X, 0)$ have a unique element.

The zero object is unique up to isomorphism.

4. EQUALIZER AND COEQUALIZER

Conceptually, an equalizer is the universal pair that captures precisely the part of the domain on which two parallel morphisms agree.

4.1. Definition. Let \mathcal{C} be a category and let $f, g: X_0 \rightarrow X_1$ be morphisms in \mathcal{C} . An equalizer of the pair (f, g) is a pair (K, k) , where $K \in \mathcal{C}_0$ and $k \in \mathcal{C}(K, X_0)$, such that:

- (a) $fk = gk$;
(b) if (K', k') is another pair, with $K' \in \mathcal{C}_0$ and $k' \in \mathcal{C}(K', X_0)$, such that $fk' = gk'$, then there exists a unique morphism $u: K' \rightarrow K$ such that k' factors through k , i.e., $k' = ku$.

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} K & \xrightarrow{k} & X_0 & \begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{f} \\ \xrightarrow{g} \end{array} & X_1 \\ \uparrow u & \nearrow k' & & & \\ K' & & & & \end{array}$$

The following lemma establishes the uniqueness of the equalizer up to isomorphism.

4.2. Lemma. Let \mathcal{C} be a category and let $f, g: X_0 \rightarrow X_1$ be morphisms in \mathcal{C} . If there exists an equalizer of the pair (f, g) , then it is unique up to isomorphism.

If (K, k) and (K', k') are equalizers of f and g , then there exists a unique isomorphism $u : K' \rightarrow K$ such that $k' = ku$. In particular, $K \cong K'$. By a standard abuse of notation, we write $K = K'$.

4.3. Lemma. Let \mathcal{C} be a category. Every equalizer is a monomorphism.

By duality, we obtain the definition of a coequalizer and the corresponding dual statements of the preceding lemmas hold. In particular, every coequalizer is an epimorphism.

5. PULLBACK AND PUSHOUT

Conceptually, a pullback is the universal cone for completing a commutative square, given two morphisms with the same target.

5.1. Definition. Let $f_1 : X_1 \rightarrow X_0$, $f_2 : X_2 \rightarrow X_0$ be morphisms with the same target in the category \mathcal{C} . A pullback of the morphisms (f_1, f_2) is a triple (X, p_1, p_2) , where $X \in \mathcal{C}_0$ and $p_1 : X \rightarrow X_1$, $p_2 : X \rightarrow X_2$ are morphisms of \mathcal{C} such that:

- (a) $f_1 p_1 = f_2 p_2$, and
- (b) if (Y, g_1, g_2) is a triple with $Y \in \mathcal{C}_0$ and $g_1 : Y \rightarrow X_1$, $g_2 : Y \rightarrow X_2$ morphisms of \mathcal{C} such that $f_1 g_1 = f_2 g_2$, then there exists a unique morphism $u : Y \rightarrow X$ such that $p_1 u = g_1$, $p_2 u = g_2$:

The uniqueness of the morphism u means that if u and v satisfy $p_1 u = p_1 v$ and $p_2 u = p_2 v$, then $u = v$.

The commutative square with vertices X, X_1, X_2, X_0 is called a Cartesian square. Dually, we obtain a pushout, which forms a cocartesian square. A commutative square that is simultaneously cartesian and cocartesian is called a bicartesian square.

6. ZERO MORPHISM

The concept of a zero morphism is required to define kernels and exact sequences.

6.1. Lemma. Let \mathcal{C} be a category with a zero object 0 . Then, for every pair of objects (X, Y) of \mathcal{C} , there exists a morphism $0_{YX} \in \mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ such that:

- (a) $f 0_{YX} = 0_{ZX}$ for every morphism $f : Y \rightarrow Z$;
- (b) $0_{YX} g = 0_{YW}$ for every morphism $g : W \rightarrow X$.

The morphisms 0_{YX} of the lemma are called the zero morphisms of the category. If a category \mathcal{C} contains a zero object, then it contains zero morphisms. The morphisms 0_{YX} are often simply denoted by 0 , the source and the target being clear from the context in each particular case.

To define exact sequences as in module theory, we need the concept of a K -category. For a commutative ring K , a category \mathcal{C} is a K -category if the sets $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ are K -modules and the composition in \mathcal{C} is K -bilinear. This notion belongs to a broader theory, which we do not develop here, and serves only as a technical background for our discussion.

7. KERNELS AND COKERNELS

The kernel of a morphism $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is the equalizer of f and the zero morphism $0 : X \rightarrow Y$. Conceptually, the kernel morphism of f is that when composed with f , results in the zero morphism.

7.1. Definition. Let \mathcal{C} be a K -category and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a morphism in \mathcal{C} . The *kernel* of f is a pair (U, u) , with $U \in \mathcal{C}_0$ and $u \in \mathcal{C}(U, X)$, such that:

- (i) $f u = 0$;
- (ii) if (U', u') is a pair with $U' \in \mathcal{C}_0$ and $u' \in \mathcal{C}(U', X)$ satisfying $f u' = 0$, then there exists a unique morphism $g : U' \rightarrow U$ such that $u g = u'$.

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 U & \xrightarrow{u} & X & \xrightarrow{f} & Y \\
 \uparrow g & \nearrow u' & & & \\
 U' & & & &
 \end{array}$$

The definition of a cokernel is obtained by duality. Both concepts require the existence of zero morphisms in the category.

We write $(U, u) = \text{Ker } f$. When referring to the object or the morphism individually, we write $U = \text{Ker } f$ and $u = \text{ker } f$, respectively. The notation for the cokernel follows the same convention, using $\text{Coker } f$ and $\text{coker } f$.

Because kernels are equalizers of f and 0 , they inherit the properties of equalizers. By Lemma 4.2, a kernel is unique up to isomorphism. If $k: K \rightarrow X$ is a kernel of f , we have $K \cong \text{Ker } f$, and by a standard abuse of notation, we write $K = \text{Ker } f$. Furthermore, Lemma 4.3 ensures that every kernel is a monomorphism. Dually, every cokernel is an epimorphism.

We state the following results.

7.2. Corollary. Let \mathcal{C} be a K -category with a zero object and $f: X \rightarrow Y$ a morphism in \mathcal{C} .

- (a) f is a monomorphism if and only if $\text{inf ker } f = 0$.
- (b) f is an epimorphism if and only if $\text{inf coker } f = 0$.

7.3. Corollary. Let \mathcal{C} be a K -category with a zero object, and let $f: X \rightarrow Y$ and $g: Y \rightarrow Z$ be morphisms in \mathcal{C} .

- (a) If f has a kernel and g is a monomorphism, then $\text{ker } f = \text{ker}(gf)$.
- (b) If g has a cokernel and f is an epimorphism, then $\text{coker } g = \text{coker}(gf)$.

7.4. Corollary. Let \mathcal{C} be a K -category with a zero object and X, Y objects of \mathcal{C} . Then $\text{ker } 0_{YX} = 1_X$ and $\text{coker } 0_{YX} = 1_Y$.

8. IMAGE AND COIMAGE

The structure of a K -module on the sets $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$ finds inspiration in the categories of groups, modules, and vector spaces. These categories present another axiom: the possibility to form products and coproducts. The addition of this axiom to a K -category yields the definition of a linear category. Let K be a commutative ring. A K -category \mathcal{C} is a linear category if every finite family of objects in \mathcal{C} admits a product and a coproduct in \mathcal{C} . This notion belongs to a broader theory, which we do not develop here, and serves only as a technical background for our discussion.

The isomorphism theorem provides a factorization of a morphism through its image. To establish an analogue of this factorization in a linear category, we must introduce an appropriate notion of image.

8.1. Definition. Let K be a commutative ring, let \mathcal{C} be a K -linear category, and let f be a morphism of \mathcal{C} .

- (a) The image of f is the kernel of the cokernel of f .
- (b) The coimage of f is the cokernel of the kernel of f .

We denote the image object of f by $\text{Im } f = \text{Ker}(\text{Coker } f)$ and the image morphism by $\text{im } f = \text{ker}(\text{coker } f)$. Dually, we denote the coimage object by $\text{Coim } f = \text{Coker}(\text{Ker } f)$ and the coimage morphism by $\text{coim } f = \text{coker}(\text{ker } f)$.

These objects need not exist in general. However, whenever \mathcal{C} has kernels and cokernels, they exist and are unique up to isomorphism.

9. EXACT SEQUENCES

The notion of exact sequence makes sense in any category that admits zero morphisms, kernels, and cokernels.

9.1. Definition. Let \mathcal{C} be a linear category in which every morphism has a kernel and a cokernel. A finite or infinite, sequence of morphisms

$$\cdots \rightarrow X_{i-1} \xrightarrow{f_{i-1}} X_i \xrightarrow{f_i} X_{i+1} \rightarrow \cdots$$

is exact at X_i if $\text{im } f_{i-1} = \text{ker } f_i$, and it is an exact sequence if it is exact at X_i for all i .

We record the following basic characterization, which will be used later.

9.2. Examples. Let \mathcal{C} be a linear category in which every morphism admits a kernel and a cokernel.

- (i) A sequence $0 \rightarrow X \xrightarrow{f} Y$ is exact if and only if f is a monomorphism.
- (ii) A sequence $X \xrightarrow{f} Y \rightarrow 0$ is exact if and only if f is an epimorphism.

10. STRICT MORPHISMS

Following Assem [1], we know, by Lemma 4.3, that kernels are monomorphisms and cokernels are epimorphisms. The converse need not hold in general. We define the class of morphisms for which this converse holds.

10.1. Definition. Let \mathcal{C} be a linear category in which every morphism has a kernel and a cokernel. A morphism f in \mathcal{C} is called strict if it admits a factorization $f = j p$, where p is a cokernel and j is a kernel. We refer to such a factorization as a canonical factorization.

Let f be a strict morphism. Then every factorization of f as an epimorphism followed by a monomorphism, called epi–mono factorization, is unique. More precisely, suppose that $f = j' p'$ where j' is a monomorphism and p' is an epimorphism. Then there exists an isomorphism u such that $j' = j u$ and $p = u p'$. Consequently, the monomorphism is a kernel and the epimorphism is a cokernel. Moreover, if a strict morphism is both a monomorphism and an epimorphism, then it is an isomorphism.

The next corollary gives a characterization of the factorization of a strict morphism by its image and coimage, called image factorization.

10.2. Corollary. Suppose that $f = j p$, where j is a kernel and p is a cokernel. Then $j = \text{im } f$ and $p = \text{coim } f$.

The following result will be used in the proof of the Snake Lemma.

10.3. Theorem. Let k and l be composable morphisms. If k is a monomorphism, then $\text{im}(kl) = k \text{im } l$.

Proof. Consider the canonical factorization $l = (\text{im } l)p$, where p is an epimorphism. Substituting this into the composition yields $kl = (k \text{im } l)p$. Since both k and $\text{im } l$ are monomorphisms, so is $k \text{im } l$. Thus, the equation $kl = (k \text{im } l)p$ constitutes a factorization of kl . By the uniqueness of the image factorization, we conclude that $\text{im}(kl) = k \text{im } l$. \square

Finally, strictness simplifies the criteria for exactness.

10.4. Corollary.

- (a) Let $0 \rightarrow X \xrightarrow{f} Y \xrightarrow{g} Z$ be a sequence where f is a strict morphism. This sequence is exact if, and only if, $f = \ker g$.
- (b) Let $X \xrightarrow{f} Y \xrightarrow{g} Z \rightarrow 0$ be a sequence where g is a strict morphism. This sequence is exact if, and only if, $g = \text{coker } f$.

11. CARTESIAN SQUARES

In the sense of Assem [1]. Let K be a commutative ring, a K -linear category is said to be K -abelian, or simply an abelian category, if every morphism admits a kernel and a cokernel, and every morphism is strict.

Now, we discuss some properties of pullbacks and pushouts within abelian categories. We have selected two specific results that will be applied directly in the proof of the Snake Lemma.

11.1. Lemma. Consider a cartesian square in an abelian category:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X & \xrightarrow{g_2} & Y_2 \\ g_1 \downarrow & & \downarrow f_2 \\ Y_1 & \xrightarrow{f_1} & Z \end{array}$$

Then, the following properties hold:

- (a) If f_1 is an epimorphism, then g_2 is an epimorphism.
- (b) $\ker f_1 = g_1 \ker g_2$.

Proof. We demonstrate only item (b). Let $f_0: K \rightarrow Y_1$ be the kernel of f_1 . Since $f_1 f_0 = 0$ and $f_2 0 = 0$, the universal property of the Cartesian square yields a unique morphism $g_0: K \rightarrow X$ such that $g_1 g_0 = f_0$ and $g_2 g_0 = 0$. Because f_0 is a kernel, it is a monomorphism, which forces g_0 to be a monomorphism.

We claim that $g_0 = \ker g_2$. Let h be a morphism such that $g_2h = 0$. Commutativity of the square gives $f_1g_1h = f_2g_2h = 0$. Since (K, f_0) is the kernel of f_1 , there exists a unique morphism k such that $g_1h = f_0k$.

Now, observe that the morphisms h and g_0k into the pullback satisfy $g_1h = f_0k = g_1(g_0k)$ and $g_2h = 0 = g_2(g_0k)$. By the uniqueness in the definition of the pullback, it follows that $h = g_0k$. This shows that h factors through g_0 . Since g_0 is a monomorphism, we conclude $g_0 = \ker g_2$. Therefore, $\ker f_1 = f_0 = g_1g_0 = g_1 \ker g_2$.

□

12. DIAGRAM LEMMAS

Diagram lemmas are tools from homological algebra used to prove the existence of morphisms, isomorphisms, and the exactness of sequences. These results are proved in Assem [1] entirely through universal properties.

12.1. Lemma. Let $X \xrightarrow{f} Y \xrightarrow{g} Z$ be composable morphisms in an abelian category. In the commutative diagram with exact rows

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 0 & \longrightarrow & \text{Ker}(gf) & \xrightarrow{i} & X & \xrightarrow{gf} & Z \\
 & & k \downarrow & & \downarrow f & & \parallel \\
 0 & \longrightarrow & \text{Ker } g & \xrightarrow{j} & Y & \xrightarrow{g} & Z
 \end{array}$$

where i and j are the canonical injections and k is obtained by passing to kernels, the left square is cartesian;

By “passing to kernels”, we mean that since $g(fi) = 0$, the universal property of $\ker g$ guarantees the existence of a unique morphism k such that fi factors through j , that is, $jk = fi$, making the diagram commute.

By duality, reversing the arrows and replacing kernels with cokernels yields the dual result, where “passing to cokernels” similarly induces a unique morphism that makes the corresponding square cocartesian.

The lemma below is also known as the kernel-cokernel sequence lemma.

12.2. Lemma. Let $X \xrightarrow{f} Y \xrightarrow{g} Z$ be composable morphisms in an abelian category. There is an exact sequence $0 \rightarrow \text{Ker } f \rightarrow \text{Ker}(gf) \rightarrow \text{Ker } g \rightarrow \text{Coker } f \rightarrow \text{Coker}(gf) \rightarrow \text{Coker } g \rightarrow 0$, with all morphisms functorial.

It is important to understand that this proof begins with the commutative diagram with exact row and columns

where the k_i are the injections and p_1 is the projection. By passing to the kernels, we find $v : \text{Ker}(gf) \rightarrow \text{Ker } g$ such that $k_3v = fk_2$. [1]

13. SNAKE LEMMA

The Snake Lemma establishes the existence of a connecting morphism that completes a long exact sequence, whose characteristic shape gives the lemma its name. We follow the formulation and proof strategy of Assem [1].

13.1. Lemma. Let

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} X & \xrightarrow{f} & Y & \xrightarrow{g} & Z & \longrightarrow & 0 \\ & & \downarrow u & & \downarrow v & & \downarrow w \\ 0 & \longrightarrow & X & \xrightarrow{f'} & Y' & \xrightarrow{g'} & Z' \end{array}$$

be a commutative diagram with exact rows in an abelian category. There exists a morphism $\delta: \text{Ker } w \rightarrow \text{Coker } u$ such that the sequence below is exact

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} \text{ker } u & \xrightarrow{f_1} & \text{ker } v & \xrightarrow{g_1} & \text{ker } w & \longrightarrow & \\ & & & & \delta & & \\ \text{Coker } u & \xrightarrow{f_2} & \text{Coker } v & \xrightarrow{g_2} & \text{Coker } w & \longrightarrow & \end{array}$$

Moreover:

- (a) f_1 is a monomorphism if and only if f is;
- (b) g_2 is an epimorphism if and only if g is.

Proof. Since f' is a monomorphism, it follows from Lemma 7.3 that $\text{Ker } u = \text{Ker}(f'u) = \text{Ker}(vf)$. Now, let $X \xrightarrow{f} Y \xrightarrow{v} Y'$ be composable morphisms. By Lemma 12.2, we obtain an exact sequence

$$0 \longrightarrow \text{Ker } f \longrightarrow \text{Ker } u \xrightarrow{f_1} \text{Ker } v \longrightarrow \text{Coker } f = Z,$$

where, exactly as constructed in Lemma 12.2, the morphism f_1 is obtained by passing to kernels, and the morphism from $\text{Ker } v$ to $\text{Coker } f$ is the composition of g with $k_2 = \text{ker } v$. Observe that, by Corollary 10.4, we can write $Z = \text{Coker } f$.

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} 0 & & 0 & & & & \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow & & & & \\ \text{Ker } v & \xrightarrow{\quad g_1 \quad} & \text{Ker } w & & & & \\ k_2 \downarrow & & \downarrow k_3 & & & & \\ Y & \xrightarrow{g} & Z = \text{Coker } f & \longrightarrow & 0 & & \\ v \downarrow & & \downarrow w & & & & \\ Y' & \xrightarrow{g'} & Z' & & & & \end{array}$$

Since the original diagram commutes, we have $w(gk_2) = g'vk_2 = 0$. Passing to kernels yields a unique morphism $g_1: \text{Ker } v \rightarrow \text{Ker } w$ such that $k_3g_1 = gk_2$. Because the sequence obtained by Lemma 12.2 is exact at $\text{Ker } v$, we know that $\text{Im } f_1 = \text{Ker}(gk_2)$. However, since k_3 is a kernel and hence a monomorphism, we have $\text{Ker}(gk_2) = \text{Ker}(k_3g_1) = \text{Ker } g_1$. This proves the exactness of the sequence

$$0 \longrightarrow \text{Ker } f \longrightarrow \text{Ker } u \xrightarrow{f_1} \text{Ker } v \xrightarrow{g_1} \text{Ker } w,$$

where both f_1 and g_1 are obtained by passage to kernels.

We now construct the connecting morphism $\delta: \text{Ker } w \rightarrow \text{Coker } u$.

Set $k = \text{ker}(wg)$, which by commutativity is equal to $\text{ker}(g'v)$. Consider the diagram below, whose rows and rightmost column are exact:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
& & & 0 & & 0 & \\
& & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & \\
& & & \ker(wg) & \xrightarrow{g_0} & \ker w & \longrightarrow 0 \\
& \swarrow q & & \downarrow k & * & \downarrow k_3 & \\
X & \xrightarrow{f} & Y & \xrightarrow{g} & Z & \longrightarrow 0 \\
& \downarrow u & & \downarrow v & & \downarrow w & \\
0 & \longrightarrow & X' & \xrightarrow{f'} & Y' & \xrightarrow{g'} & Z'
\end{array}$$

By Lemma 12.1, there exists a morphism $g_0: \text{Ker}(wg) \rightarrow \text{Ker } w$, obtained by passage to kernels, such that the square formed by the morphisms g_0, k_3, g , and k is cartesian. Since g is an epimorphism, it follows from Lemma 11.1 that g_0 is also an epimorphism.

By the exactness of the sequence $X \xrightarrow{f} Y \xrightarrow{g} Z \rightarrow 0$, it follows from Corollary 10.4 that $g = \text{coker } f$. Consequently, $gf = 0$, which in turn implies $(wg)f = w(gf) = 0$. By the universal property of the kernel $k = \text{ker}(wg)$, this guarantees the existence of a unique morphism $\ell: X \rightarrow \text{Ker}(wg)$ such that $f = k\ell$.

We claim that the sequence

$$X \xrightarrow{\ell} \text{Ker}(wg) \xrightarrow{g_0} \text{Ker } w \longrightarrow 0$$

is exact.

To see this, first recall that we have already established g_0 as an epimorphism, which gives exactness at $\text{Ker } w$ by Example 9.2. It remains to show exactness at $\text{Ker}(wg)$. From Lemma 11.1, the cartesian square formed by g_0, k_3, g , and k yields the relation $\text{ker } g = k \text{ker } g_0$.

On the other hand, exactness at Y in the original sequence means $\text{ker } g = \text{im } f$. Substituting our factorization $f = k\ell$, we obtain $\text{ker } g = \text{im}(k\ell)$. Because k is a monomorphism, by Theorem 10.3, we have $\text{im}(k\ell) = k \text{im } \ell$.

Equating the two expressions for $\text{ker } g$, we arrive at $k \text{ker } g_0 = k \text{im } \ell$. Finally, since k is a monomorphism, and is therefore left-cancellable, we conclude that $\text{ker } g_0 = \text{im } \ell$, proving the exactness of the sequence.

Since the bottom sequence $X' \xrightarrow{f'} Y' \xrightarrow{g'} Z'$ is exact, $f' = \text{ker } g'$ by Corollary 10.4. By the commutativity of the rightmost bottom square, we have $g'v = wg$. Thus, composing this with $k = \text{ker}(wg)$ on the right, we obtain $g'vk = wwk = 0$. The universal property of the kernel $f' = \text{ker } g'$ yields a unique morphism $q: \text{Ker}(wg) \rightarrow X'$ satisfying $f'q = vk$.

Let us prove that the triangle formed by ℓ, q , and u commutes. Composing $f'q = vk$ with ℓ on the right, we get $f'q\ell = vk\ell$. Recall that $k\ell = f$, so $f'q\ell = vk\ell = vf$. By the commutativity of the leftmost square, we also know that $vf = f'u$.

Equating both expressions, we arrive at $f'q\ell = f'u$. Finally, since f' is a monomorphism, it is left-cancellable, allowing us to conclude that $q\ell = u$.

The commutativity relation $q\ell = u$ established above allows us to construct the connecting morphism $\delta: \text{Ker } w \rightarrow \text{Coker } u$. It is the unique morphism obtained by passage to cokernels in the following commutative diagram with exact rows by the dual of the Lemma 12.1:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
X & \xrightarrow{\ell} & \text{Ker}(wg) & \xrightarrow{g_0} & \text{Ker } w & \longrightarrow & 0 \\
\parallel & & \downarrow q & & \downarrow \delta & & \\
X & \xrightarrow{u} & X' & \xrightarrow{\ell_1} & \text{Coker } u & \longrightarrow & 0
\end{array}$$

where $\ell_1 = \text{coker } u$.

We claim that the sequence

$$\text{Ker}(vk) \longrightarrow \text{Ker } w \xrightarrow{\delta} \text{Coker } u.$$

is exact.

To see this, we start applying Lemma 12.2 to the composable morphisms $X \xrightarrow{\ell} \text{Ker}(wg) \xrightarrow{g_0} \text{Ker } w$, which yields the exact sequence:

$$\text{Ker } q \longrightarrow \text{Coker } \ell \longrightarrow \text{Coker}(q\ell).$$

Let us analyze the terms of this sequence. First, since $q\ell = u$, we trivially have $\text{Coker}(q\ell) = \text{Coker } u$. Second, the exactness of the sequence $X \xrightarrow{\ell} \text{Ker}(wg) \xrightarrow{g_0} \text{Ker } w \rightarrow 0$ proved above implies that $\text{Coker } \ell = \text{Ker } w$ by Corollary 10.4. Finally, recall that $f'q = vk$. Since f' is a monomorphism, we obtain $\text{Ker } q = \text{Ker}(f'q) = \text{Ker}(vk)$.

Substituting these three identifications back into the sequence $\text{Ker } q \longrightarrow \text{Coker } \ell \longrightarrow \text{Coker}(q\ell)$, we proved the exactness of the sequence $\text{Ker}(vk) \longrightarrow \text{Ker } w \xrightarrow{\delta} \text{Coker } u$ where δ is precisely the morphism from $\text{Coker } \ell$

to $\text{Coker}(q\ell)$ provided by the Lemma 12.2 because of the uniqueness of the morphism obtained by passage to cokernels.

We claim that $\text{Ker}(vk) = \text{Ker } v$. To this end, we apply Lemma 12.2 once again, which yields the exact sequence

$$0 = \text{Ker } k \longrightarrow \text{Ker}(vk) \xrightarrow{i} \text{Ker } v \xrightarrow{t} \text{Coker } k,$$

where $\text{Ker } k = 0$ because of Corollary 7.2 and the morphism t is the composition $p'k_2$ in the following commutative diagram with exact rows:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} 0 & \longrightarrow & \text{Ker } v & \xrightarrow{k_2} & Y & \xrightarrow{v} & Y' \\ & & & & \downarrow p' & \searrow wg & \downarrow g' \\ & & & & \text{Coker } k & \xrightarrow{j'} & Z' \end{array}$$

In this diagram, $j'p'$ is the canonical factorization of $g'v = wg$. The commutativity gives us $j't = j'p'k_2 = g'vk_2 = 0 = j'0$. Since j' is a monomorphism, we have $t = 0$.

Now, let us analyze the morphism $i: \text{Ker}(vk) \rightarrow \text{Ker } v$ from our exact sequence. We already know that i is a monomorphism because of the Example 9.2. Furthermore, exactness at $\text{Ker } v$ implies that $\text{im } i = \text{ker } t$. Since we have just established that $t = 0$, its kernel is the identity morphism on $\text{Ker } v$ by Corollary 7.4, allowing us to write $\text{im } i = 1_{\text{Ker } v}$.

From the canonical factorization of i , we obtain $i = (\text{im } i)(\text{coim } i) = 1_{\text{Ker } v} \text{coim } i = \text{coim } i$. Because every coimage is an epimorphism, it follows that i is an epimorphism. Working in an abelian category, every morphism that is both a monomorphism and an epimorphism is necessarily an isomorphism. Consequently, $\text{Ker}(vk) \cong \text{Ker } v$. By a standard abuse of notation, we will simply write $\text{Ker}(vk) = \text{Ker } v$.

Then, the exact sequence $\text{Ker}(vk) \longrightarrow \text{Ker } w \xrightarrow{\delta} \text{Coker } u$ can be rewritten as

$$\text{Ker } v \xrightarrow{g_1} \text{Ker } w \xrightarrow{\delta} \text{Coker } u$$

by the uniqueness of the morphism g_1 obtained by passage to kernels. We have thus proved the existence of the exact sequence

$$0 \longrightarrow \text{Ker } f \longrightarrow \text{Ker } u \xrightarrow{f_1} \text{Ker } v \xrightarrow{g_1} \text{Ker } w \xrightarrow{\delta} \text{Coker } u.$$

By splicing this sequence with its dual, we obtain the famous “snake” sequence:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccccccc} 0 & \longrightarrow & \text{Ker } f & \longrightarrow & \text{Ker } u & \xrightarrow{f_1} & \text{Ker } v & \xrightarrow{g_1} & \text{Ker } w & \longrightarrow & \text{Coker } u \\ & & & & & & & & & \searrow \delta & \\ & & & & & & & & & & \text{Coker } u \xrightarrow{f_2} \text{Coker } v \xrightarrow{g_2} \text{Coker } w \longrightarrow \text{Coker } g \longrightarrow 0 \end{array}$$

In particular, by Example 9.2, the morphism $\text{Ker } f \rightarrow \text{Ker } u$ is a monomorphism, and by Corollary 10.4, it is the kernel of f_1 ; thus, $\text{Ker } f_1 = \text{Ker } f$. Again, by Example 9.2, if f is a monomorphism, then $\text{Ker } f = \text{Ker } f_1 = 0$, which implies that f_1 is a monomorphism. Analogously, we obtain the converse. Dually, g_2 is an epimorphism if and only if g is.

This completes the proof of (a) and (b). □

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